

Cataract after laser treatment of retinopathy of prematurity – challenges in pediatric ophthalmology

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Abstract

Retinopathy of prematurity (ROP) is one of the most serious eye diseases affecting prematurely born infants. Modern treatment methods, including laser photocoagulation, have significantly reduced the incidence of blindness and severe visual impairment due to tractional retinal detachment, macular folds, or excessive myopia. However, long-term complications are still observed in some patients, among which cataract formation holds particular significance. The aim of this study was to evaluate the risk of cataract development in premature infants treated for type 1 ROP. We performed a retrospective study during which we studied 660 premature infants (352 boys and 308 girls) for a period of 5 years. Of these, 145 children (21.97%) were diagnosed with ROP at different stages. A total of 97 children (66.9% of those with ROP) underwent treatment for type 1 ROP. Of these, 80 were treated with laser photocoagulation, and 17 with intravitreal anti-VEGF medications. In the remaining 48 children, spontaneous regression of the disease occurred, and no treatment was necessary. During the study period, only one child (1.25%) developed a cataract. The proper balance between laser energy and number of laser spots is crucial for avoiding complications such as cataract formation. Laser therapy for ROP saves the vision of thousands of children worldwide, but it carries a risk of later complications, including cataract formation. Early detection, along with appropriate surgical treatment, optical correction, and occlusion therapy, is crucial for amblyopia prevention and normal visual development. These patients require long-term follow-up and multidisciplinary care to ensure maximum visual potential.

Keywords

Retinopathy of prematurity, cataract, laser photocoagulation, pediatric ophthalmology

Introduction

Retinopathy of prematurity (ROP) is a leading cause of preventable childhood blindness. It is a multifactorial disease of prematurely born babies associated with abnormal development of the retina and its blood vessels, leading to pathological retinal vascularization (Terry 1946; Chernodrinska et al. 2003; Mutlu et al. 2013; Khokhar et

al. 2022; Kaur et al. 2025). The disease was first described by Terry in 1942 as retrolental fibroplasia, recognized as a major cause of childhood blindness in the United States. Terry linked the disease to the prematurity of the infant. As survival rates of preterm infants increased, so did the incidence of retrolental fibroplasia, which had previously been rare. In 74% of the cases, the premature babies had a birth weight under 1500 grams (Terry 1946).

There have been three ROP “epidemics” (Mladenov 2016; Hong et al. 2022; Chiang et al. 2021):

- The first, between the 1940s and 1950s in high-income countries, was associated with unmonitored high-concentration oxygen therapy. After oxygen therapy protocols were introduced, the incidence dropped sharply.
- The second epidemic, during the 1970s, was linked to improved neonatal care, which allowed more babies with very low and extremely low gestational age and weight to survive (Hong et al. 2022; Kaur et al. 2025).
- The third epidemic has been observed from the mid-1990s to the present, emerging in low- and middle-income countries (Eastern Europe, Latin America, East and South Asia, and Sub-Saharan Africa). These regions had high rates of preterm births and inconsistent neonatal care, along with the lack of mandatory ROP screening protocols.

In high-income countries today, ROP is mainly associated with extreme prematurity, characterized by incomplete retinal vascularization and, to a lesser extent, oxygen-induced injury.

Early diagnosis and timely treatment prevent irreversible blindness or severe visual impairment in most cases. Screening is the crucial step in ROP management, identifying babies with type 1 ROP that require urgent treatment.

Screening criteria (Jefferies 2010; Mladenov et al. 2016; Berrocal et al. 2021):

- Any infant with birth weight ≤ 1501 g and gestational age ≤ 32 weeks must be screened for ROP.
- Singleton infants with birth weight > 1501 g and gestational age > 32 weeks, deemed high-risk by the attending neonatologist due to one or more additional risk factors, should also be screened. These risk factors include advanced necrotizing enterocolitis, significant acidosis, intraventricular hemorrhage (grade II or higher), stroke, prolonged oxygen therapy with mechanical ventilation, shock or hypotension, prolonged severe anemia and transfusions, significant perinatal metabolic disturbances, intra-uterine growth restriction, and surgical intervention under general anesthesia during the neonatal period.

Treatment modalities include cryotherapy, anti-VEGF, and laser therapy.

In 1986, cryotherapy of the avascular retina was introduced as a safe and effective surgical technique for threshold ROP (CRYO-ROP trial). The treatment is based on the disease’s pathogenesis—ablation of the peripheral ischemic retina reduces the release of vasoactive substances that stimulate neovascularization.

Cryotherapy is performed transconjunctivally or transsclerally under direct visualization, under either local or general anesthesia. The entire avascular retina peripheral to the ridge must be treated, avoiding coagulation directly

on the ridge. Avascular areas must be completely treated without overlapping burns (Hindle et al. 1986; Mutlu et al. 2013; Hong et al. 2022).

Laser treatment is recommended in the following cases of type 1 ROP (DeJonge et al. 2000; Oskar et al. 2021):

- **Zone I:** Any stage of ROP with plus disease.
- **Zone I:** Stage 3 ROP without plus disease.
- **Zone II:** Stage 2 or 3 with plus disease.

Treatment should ideally be initiated within 72 hours (Oskar et al. 2021).

The principle of laser therapy is similar to cryotherapy—ablation of the peripheral avascular retina to stop the release of proangiogenic factors (primarily vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF)), responsible for neovascularization, subsequent traction, and retinal detachment. The procedure is most commonly performed transpupillary.

Laser therapy is considered the “gold standard” for ROP treatment and has largely replaced cryotherapy due to its atraumatic nature and favorable anatomical and functional outcomes.

Due to reduced trauma and fewer postoperative complications, and because cryotherapy is less effective in Zone I, argon and diode lasers were introduced in clinical practice for treating pre-threshold ROP (ETROP study). Lasers offer several advantages over cryotherapy: they are more portable, less traumatic, and better tolerated (Brown et al. 1990; Mutlu et al. 2013; Khokhar et al. 2017; Hong et al. 2022).

The second phase of ROP pathophysiology involves a significant increase in VEGF levels, which led to the introduction of anti-VEGF medications. Treatment should not begin earlier than 31 weeks postmenstrual age, as premature application may lead to treatment failure (Mutlu et al. 2013; Salman et al. 2015; Tran et al. 2018; Alzuabi et al. 2022; Strube et al. 2022; Sanghi et al. 2024).

Anti-VEGF therapy is especially promising for type 1 ROP in Zone I and posterior Zone II and APROP.

The following medications are used (Mutlu et al. 2013; Salman et al. 2015; Tran et al. 2018; Alzuabi et al. 2022):

- Pegaptanib (Macugen)—Selectively blocks some forms of VEGF-A.
- Ranibizumab (Lucentis)—Antibody fragment with good tissue penetration; blocks all forms of VEGF-A (non-selective).
- Bevacizumab (Avastin)—Full antibody with weaker tissue penetration but longer half-life; blocks all VEGF-A forms (non-selective); used off-label in ophthalmology.
- VEGF-trap (Aflibercept)—Blocks VEGF-A, VEGF-B, and PGF.

The latest ROP guidelines, which include treatment with laser photocoagulation and anti-VEGF medications, lead to significantly reduced structural changes causing irreversible blindness, including retinal detachment. However, there are reported causes of late-onset compli-

cations, one of which is a cataract. The aim of our study is to evaluate the risk of cataract incidence after laser photocoagulation for type 1 ROP and its correlation with the number of laser impulses and energy used.

Patients and methods

This retrospective study analyzed the data acquired between 01 January 2019 and 31 December 2023, during which we examined 660 children (352 boys and 308 girls) (Table 1) who met the ROP screening criteria for premature infants in Bulgaria.

Table 1. Distribution of examined children by sex, birth mechanism, presence of a twin, method of conception, and fertilization method.

Criteria	Category	Total number (N)	Percentage (%)
Sex	Boys	352	53.3%
	Girls	308	46.7%
Birth mechanism	Caesarean section	450	68.2%
	Normal labor	210	31.8%
Presence of a twin	Single child	504	76.36%
	First twin	108	16.36%
	Second twin	48	7.28%
	Third twin	0	0.0%
In vitro fertilization	No	649	98.3%
	Yes	11	1.7%

A total of 11 children (1.7%) were conceived via *in vitro* fertilization (IVF)—six boys and five girls.

The average gestational age of the preterm infants was 30.97 weeks (30.94 weeks for boys and 31.0 weeks for girls). The average birth weight was 1498.95 g (1532.9 g for boys and 1460.34 g for girls). The lowest recorded birth weight was 560 g, and the highest—3620 g.

Patients were divided into two main groups and two subgroups:

- **Group I:** Preterm infants without ROP (Stage 0)—515 children.
- **Group II:** Preterm infants who developed ROP (Stages 1–5)—145 children.
 - **Subgroup II-A:** Developed ROP, no treatment needed; spontaneous regression occurred—48 children.
 - **Subgroup II-B:** Developed ROP and required treatment (laser and/or intravitreal anti-VEGF therapy)—97 children.

For screening, we used dilating drops, which included a combination of 0.5% cyclopentolate and 2.5% phenylephrine, applied every 10–15 minutes. Diluted cyclopentolate is preferred to reduce systemic side effects. Atropine is avoided. Excess solution is wiped off to prevent systemic absorption and complications such as tachycardia and hyperthermia.

The screening was done with the use of indirect ophthalmoscopy, conducted by a trained ophthalmologist in the neonatal clinics. If any stage of ROP was diagnosed, the babies were further examined with a RetCam digital camera to document and follow the cases. Patients diagnosed with type 1 ROP were treated with either laser photocoagulation or an anti-VEGF medication (Eylea™).

Laser photocoagulation was conducted using an 810 nm wavelength diode laser, which is the standard, preferred treatment for ROP. It was applied via an indirect ophthalmoscope. Power was adjusted according to the pigmentation of the retina, typically starting around 300 mW, and 0.15 s duration per spot.

Results

The criteria for ROP screening in the territory of Bulgaria include all babies born before the 32nd week of gestational age and weight at birth below 1500 grams or any infant that is considered at risk by the neonatologists. For a period of 5 years, 660 infants had been examined, of which 515 had no structural changes associated with ROP, and in 145 we diagnosed different stages of ROP. Detailed information is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Distribution of children by ROP stage.

ROP Stage	Number of children
Stage 0	515
Stage 1	31
Stage 2	41
Stage 3	66
Stage 4	2
Stage 5	5

In a comprehensive analysis, it is established that the incidence of ROP is significantly higher in infants born before the 30th week of gestational age. Detailed information is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. ROP incidence by gestational age.

Gestational age	ROP incidence (%)
< 28 weeks	54.9%
28–30 weeks	27.1%
30–32 weeks	10.1%
32–34 weeks	4.1%
34–37 weeks	3.8%

A total of 97 children (66.9%) of those diagnosed with ROP underwent treatment. In 80 babies, laser photocoagulation was performed, and in 17, the treatment was with an anti-VEGF medication (Eylea™). In 48 infants, we observed spontaneous regression. Detailed information is shown in Table 4.

We used a diode laser with an 810 nm wavelength. Typically, around 1,000 laser spots per eye were applied. The

Table 4. Treatment of patients with ROP.

Type of treatment	Number of treated children
Laser photocoagulation	80
Intravitreal anti-VEGF	17
Spontaneous regression (no treatment)	48

higher the number of burns, the greater the risk of damaging adjacent structures.

- At power levels above 500 mW and > 1000 spots per eye, the risk of a thermal cataract rises significantly (Nicoară 2019; Khokhar et al. 2022):

Among the 80 laser-treated children, one child (1.25%) developed a cataract. That case required more than 1,000 laser impulses due to a highly pigmented retina. No cataract formation was observed in patients treated with the anti-VEGF medication, who were primarily infants with APROP.

Discussion

This analysis emphasizes the importance of routine ROP screening and the careful selection and dosing of treatment to minimize complications such as cataract formation.

Reported incidence of cataracts after laser treatment for ROP ranges from 0.003% to 6% (Davitt et al. 2013; Nguyen and Yen 2017; Khokhar et al. 2022). This correlates with our data, which is in the lower percentages of incidence. Argon lasers have the highest risk of cataract development (Khokhar et al. 2022).

A diode laser (810 nm wavelength) was used in clinical practice. Laser power was individually adjusted based on retinal pigmentation:

- In highly pigmented retinas, lower energy was used due to the heat-inducing photochemical reaction.
- In hypopigmented retinas, higher energy was required to achieve a therapeutic effect (Jalali et al. 2010).

Higher energy settings in hypopigmented eyes increase the risk of lens heating and subsequent thermal cataract formation (Khokhar et al. 2022). Cataracts can appear months or years after the intervention and impair normal visual development.

Main mechanisms include thermal injury to retrolental tissue and anterior hyaloid membrane; secondary changes due to chronic inflammation and structural retinal changes; and multiple risk factors like low birth weight, prematurity, and prior vitreoretinal interventions (Khokhar et al. 2022).

Cataract development in these patients is particularly concerning because it occurs during a critical period of visual development. If it is not treated promptly, it can cause amblyopia. Additionally, the surgical removal is technically challenging due to anatomical changes from

prior treatment. Surgical cataract removal is the primary treatment approach. In preterm infants or those with ROP, IOL implantation decisions are individualized due to unstable ocular growth (Veleva 2018). Postoperative care includes aphakia correction (glasses or contact lenses if no IOL), strict amblyopia therapy (occlusion of the better eye), and long-term monitoring for glaucoma and retinal complications. High myopia after laser therapy has been a documented complication, especially when avascular areas in the posterior pole are treated. The extent of the treated area and the number of laser burns are critical (Hwang et al. 2022). Identified risk factors for cataract formation are also persistent fetal vasculature, accidental laser burns on the iris or ciliary body, and combined laser modalities.

Contributing mechanisms for the formation of a cataract:

1. Thermal injury

- Total laser energy (type, power, duration, number of burns) correlates with cataract risk.
- Lens proteins and hemoglobin absorb laser energy, especially when tunica vasculosa lentis persists.
- Diode lasers (810 nm) are less absorbed by hemoglobin, resulting in fewer cataracts than argon lasers (Davitt et al. 2013; Quan et al. 2015; Khokhar et al. 2022).

2. Persistent fetal vasculature

- Premature infants retain some tunica vasculosa lentis, which absorbs laser energy.
- This disrupts the anterior lens capsule's permeability, leading to osmotic imbalance and cataract.

In aggressive ROP (A-ROP), more severe cases show:

- Iris neovascularization
- Poor pupillary dilation
- Vitreous haze
- Large avascular retinal areas
- Severe "plus disease"

These require higher power, longer durations, and more applications, therefore greater energy, and present a higher risk for cataract formation (Davitt et al. 2013; Khokhar et al. 2017; Berrocal et al. 2021; Khokhar et al. 2022).

3. Anterior segment ischemia

- Blood supply comes from the anastomosis of the anterior and long posterior ciliary arteries. Damage to these may cause ischemia with conjunctival injection, corneal edema, shallow anterior chamber, hyphema, cataract, and posterior synechiae. In the late stage, there have been reports of hypotony, iris atrophy, ciliary body atrophy, and progression to phthisis bulbi.

4. Uveal effusion

- High thermal energy and immature blood-retinal barrier may lead to uveal effusion syndrome.
- This can rotate the ciliary body forward, followed by a shallow anterior chamber, leading to lens-cornea contact and cataract (Davitt et al. 2013; Nicoară 2019; Khokhar et al. 2022).

Conclusion

Although the diode laser is an effective and preferred method for controlling ROP, individual energy adjustment based on the pigmentation of the fundus and careful dosing of the number of impulses are critically important. Excessive load (high power and a large number of coagulates) creates conditions for thermal damage to the lens and the development of cataracts. This requires a careful balance between treatment effectiveness and minimizing the risk of complications.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

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Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Alexandrovska University Hospital. The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Ethics Committee of Alexandrovska University Hospital, Sofia (protocol code 1 and date of approval 23 January 2026).

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Author contributions

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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